

Supplementary Data 3. Distribution of BGCs in *Pseudomonas*: The following trees represent the number of predominant types of BGCs.

Phylogenetic tree of 194 *Pseudomonas* genomes built with UBCG and annotated with iTOL. Green bars represents number of NRPS clusters. Bar, 1 substitution per position.

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Phylogenetic tree of 194 *Pseudomonas* genomes built with UBCG and annotated with iTOL. Brown bars represents number of arylpolyenes clusters. Bar, 1 substitution per position.

Tree scale: 1

Phylogenetic tree of 194 *Pseudomonas* genomes built with UBCG and annotated with iTOL. Blue bars represents number of bacteriocin clusters. Bar, 1 substitution per position.

Tree scale: 1

Phylogenetic tree of 194 *Pseudomonas* genomes built with UBCG and annotated with iTOL. Light green bars represents number of NAGGN clusters. Bar, 1 substitution per position. Green

Tree scale: 1

Phylogenetic tree of 194 *Pseudomonas* genomes built with UBCG and annotated with iTOL. Green bars represents number of NRPS-like clusters. Bar, 1 substitution per position.

Tree scale: 1 |-----|

Phylogenetic tree of 194 *Pseudomonas* genomes built with UBCG and annotated with iTOL. Red bars represents number of siderophore clusters. Bar, 1 substitution per position.

Tree scale: 1

Phylogenetic tree of 194 *Pseudomonas* genomes built with UBCG and annotated with iTOL. Orange bars represents number of PKS clusters. Bar, 1 substitution per position.

Tree scale: 1